

Ion-Solvent Interaction of Sodium Iodide and Lithium Nitrate in *N,N*-Dimethylformamide + Ethanol Mixtures at Various Temperatures

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The densities, viscosities and ultrasonic velocities of sodium iodide and lithium nitrate in dimethylformamide + ethanol mixtures have been measured as a function of amide concentration and temperature. Viscosity and ultrasonic velocity are fitted by empirical equations stating their dependence on composition of the mixtures. The adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length, relative association, acoustic impedance, molar sound velocity, enthalpy and entropy of activation of viscous flow have been calculated. The variations of these properties with amide concentration in the mixtures indicate strong ion-solvent interaction. Preferential solvation of the ions is also discussed.

Electrolyte solutions in amide + alcohol mixtures are of considerable theoretical and industrial importance. The present investigation is concerned with ion-solvent interactions of sodium iodide and lithium nitrate in dimethylformamide (DMF) + ethanol mixtures. DMF is aprotic and practically unassociated¹. It belongs to the so called 'supersolvent' owing to its miscibility with almost all common polar and non-polar solvents², probably due to its high polarity with quite large dipole moment and a moderately high dielectric constant ($\mu = 3.86$ and $\epsilon = 36.71$ at 298.15 K)³. On the other hand, ethanol has relatively low value of dipole moment and dielectric constant ($\mu = 1.69$ and $\epsilon = 24.55$ at 298.15 K)³, yet self-associated through hydrogen bonding into chain-like associates³. Hence, DMF + ethanol will be an interesting solvent combination for the study of ion-solvent interactions in ternary systems containing electrolyte.

In the present work, the density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (u) of 0.1 M NaI and 1.0 M LiNO₃ in DMF + ethanol mixtures at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 and 318.15 K have been measured. Acoustical parameters, such as adiabatic compressibility (β), intermolecular free length (L_f), relative association (R_A), acoustic impedance (Z) and molar sound velocity (R_m) including the enthalpy (ΔH^*) and entropy (ΔS^*) of activation of viscous flow have been computed. These parameters are used to explain the ion-solvent interactions in NaI + DMF + ethanol and LiNO₃ + DMF + ethanol ternary systems. The preferential solvation of the ions by liquid components is also discussed.

Results and Discussion

The experimental values of ρ , η and u of 0.1 M NaI and 1.0 M LiNO₃ in DMF + ethanol binary mixtures as function of DMF mol% and temperature are given in Table 1(a-c). The dependence of η on mole fraction, x of DMF in the mixtures was checked by using the polynomial equation,

$$\eta = \sum_{i=1}^5 \eta_i x^{i-1} \quad (1)$$

TABLE 1(a)—DENSITY (ρ , kg m⁻³) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF AMIDE CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE

Mol% DMF	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	318.15 K
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	800.2	795.8	791.4	787.1	782.7
7.71	816.4	811.9	807.5	803.0	798.6
15.80	834.4	829.9	825.4	820.8	816.2
24.32	851.6	847.0	842.2	837.6	832.9
33.30	865.9	861.6	857.3	852.9	848.6
42.78	881.5	877.0	872.5	868.1	863.6
52.78	897.8	893.2	888.5	883.8	879.2
63.38	913.8	909.0	904.4	899.8	895.1
74.61	928.0	923.5	918.9	914.4	909.8
86.53	946.2	941.7	937.5	932.4	927.1
99.22	957.9	953.3	948.7	944.8	939.4
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	840.9	836.9	833.0	828.9	824.8
7.32	859.1	855.1	851.1	847.1	843.1
14.99	875.4	871.4	867.4	863.4	859.4
23.03	892.7	888.6	884.5	880.4	876.3
31.48	907.1	902.9	898.6	894.3	890.1
40.36	921.5	916.7	912.5	908.3	904.0
49.73	938.0	933.7	929.6	925.3	921.2
59.59	952.6	948.4	944.1	939.7	935.5
70.03	970.7	966.4	962.1	957.8	953.6
81.03	982.7	978.4	974.1	969.7	965.4
92.71	998.7	994.4	991.0	985.7	981.4

The η_i coefficients were evaluated by means of the least-squares method and are presented in Table 2 along with the standard deviations $\sigma(\eta)$ at each investigated temperature. The goodness of this fit equation is ascertained by an average uncertainty of $\pm 1.686 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\pm 3.827 \times 10^{-6}$ kg m⁻¹ s⁻¹ for NaI + DMF + ethanol and LiNO₃ + DMF + ethanol systems respectively. The authors have used similar polynomials in order to establish the dependence of ultrasonic velocity on composition of the ternary mixtures. The dependence of u on mole fraction, x of DMF in the mixtures was checked by the equation,

TABLE 1(b)—VISCOSITY (η , 10^{-3} kg m⁻¹s⁻¹) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF AMIDE CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE

Mol%					
DMF	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	318.15 K
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	1.214	1.098	0.995	0.911	0.835
7.71	1.098	1.005	0.922	0.848	0.778
15.80	1.019	0.940	0.863	0.798	0.736
24.32	0.967	0.899	0.827	0.769	0.713
33.30	0.922	0.860	0.796	0.743	0.693
42.78	0.918	0.843	0.781	0.732	0.683
52.78	0.892	0.831	0.773	0.726	0.682
63.38	0.891	0.835	0.775	0.729	0.685
74.61	0.886	0.834	0.777	0.733	0.689
86.53	0.889	0.837	0.780	0.735	0.692
99.22	0.897	0.842	0.788	0.744	0.703
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	2.353	2.111	1.884	1.706	1.536
7.32	2.249	2.020	1.810	1.638	1.484
14.99	2.089	1.893	1.708	1.553	1.419
23.03	2.020	1.823	1.642	1.505	1.374
31.48	1.895	1.725	1.569	1.441	1.323
40.36	1.808	1.653	1.512	1.393	1.288
49.73	1.895	1.645	1.508	1.357	1.289
59.59	1.786	1.625	1.501	1.388	1.286
70.03	1.788	1.641	1.506	1.396	1.291
81.03	1.815	1.668	1.517	1.409	1.301
92.71	1.851	1.705	1.564	1.470	1.340

TABLE 1(c)—ULTRASONIC VELOCITY (u , m s⁻¹) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF AMIDE CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE

Mol%					
DMF	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	318.15 K
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	1153.7	1140.2	1120.5	1102.5	1089.7
7.71	1188.8	1170.2	1162.3	1146.5	1125.1
15.80	1224.8	1299.7	1195.1	1174.8	1155.1
24.32	1256.0	1239.7	1226.2	1205.7	1184.2
33.30	1291.4	1271.7	1259.1	1238.0	1225.2
42.78	1322.5	1305.1	1282.2	1271.4	1254.5
52.78	1356.2	1336.8	1312.5	1297.2	1281.7
63.38	1385.1	1364.8	1349.1	1331.4	1316.5
74.61	1412.5	1369.8	1378.0	1359.4	1344.0
86.53	1440.5	1423.7	1402.2	1387.4	1368.2
99.22	1470.0	1448.8	1421.0	1414.0	1389.7
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	1204.5	1185.0	1170.0	1152.9	1149.0
7.32	1239.0	1223.1	1205.6	1189.7	1174.3
14.99	1275.0	1257.4	1241.6	1225.7	1209.4
23.03	1306.3	1294.5	1276.7	1258.7	1241.6
31.48	1341.0	1325.1	1379.6	1288.7	1274.1
40.36	1369.7	1354.7	1336.3	1318.7	1314.1
49.73	1404.4	1388.1	1371.4	1354.3	1336.7
59.59	1454.6	1438.6	1419.4	1403.1	1383.8
70.03	1477.7	1459.3	1439.6	1422.9	1404.4
81.03	1501.7	1482.8	1464.4	1447.3	1428.4
92.71	1535.1	1518.4	1500.8	1480.7	1462.7

TABLE 2—COEFFICIENTS, η_i OF EQN. (1) AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS σ (η) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES

T K	η_1	η_2	η_3	η_4	η_5	$\sigma(\eta) \times 10^3$
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol						
298.15	1.212	-1.705	3.586	-3.503	1.310	4.103
303.15	1.097	-1.323	2.446	-1.992	0.615	2.542
308.15	0.995	-1.097	1.981	-1.565	0.475	1.343
313.15	0.911	-1.944	1.758	-1.417	0.437	1.558
318.15	0.834	-0.843	1.696	-1.482	0.498	1.480
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol						
298.15	2.358	-1.679	-0.186	3.656	-2.310	12.471
303.15	2.115	-1.469	0.101	2.660	-1.702	8.987
308.15	1.890	-1.314	0.715	1.111	-0.829	8.408
313.15	1.710	-1.183	1.097	0.016	-0.141	8.518
318.15	1.541	-0.902	0.583	0.691	-0.489	6.192

$$\ln u = \sum_{i=1}^5 \ln u_i x^{i-1} \quad (2)$$

The results of this fit equation are presented in Table 3 along with the standard deviations σ ($\ln u$) at each investigated temperature. Equation (2) reproduces the experimental values of u with an average uncertainty of $\pm 0.186\%$ and $\pm 0.253\%$ units of u for the systems under study. The significance of data fitting using similar polynomials in reproducing the experimental values of ρ , η and u has also been reported for binary^{4,5} and ternary⁶ systems.

TABLE 3—COEFFICIENTS, $\ln u_i$ OF EQN. (2) AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS σ ($\ln u$) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES

T K	$\ln u_1$	$\ln u_2$	$\ln u_3$	$\ln u_4$	$\ln u_5$	$\sigma(\ln u) \times 10^3$
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol						
298.15	7.051	0.395	-0.168	-0.035	0.052	0.702
303.15	7.038	0.399	-0.233	0.113	-0.037	1.214
308.15	7.022	0.492	-0.655	0.721	-0.314	1.653
313.15	7.007	0.461	-0.484	0.467	-0.197	1.845
318.15	6.994	0.393	-0.173	0.433	-0.020	1.820
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol						
298.15	7.095	0.390	-0.216	0.181	-0.108	3.082
303.15	7.078	0.429	-0.305	0.244	-0.115	3.400
308.15	7.065	0.417	-0.241	0.133	-0.052	3.240
313.15	7.051	0.431	-0.322	0.310	-0.157	3.402
318.15	7.039	0.408	-0.221	0.137	-0.068	3.219

The values of ρ and u have been used to evaluate β , L_f , R_A , Z and R_m with the help of the relations^{1,7},

$$\beta = u^{-2} \rho^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$L_f = K u \rho^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

$$R_A = (\rho/\rho_0)(u_0/u)^{1/3} \quad (5)$$

$$Z = u \rho \quad (6)$$

$$R_m = V u^{1/3} \quad (7)$$

where ρ_0 and u_0 are the density and ultrasonic velocity of the solvent (DMF + ethanol), K is a temperature-dependent constant [= (93.875 + 0.375T) $\times 10^{-8}$] and V the molar volume of the mixtures. The variations of β , L_f , Z and R_m with mol% of DMF and temperature are given in Tables 4–8. It is evident from the Tables 1(c) and 5 that the variation

of u through the mixtures of ternary systems investigated depends upon the value of L_f . In the present study, u increases with the corresponding decrease in L_f . Similar results have also been reported for monochloroacetic acid in nitrobenzene + ethanol⁸ and KBr in formamide + water⁹ systems.

TABLE 4—ADIABATIC COMPRESSIBILITY (β , 10^{-10} m²N⁻¹) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF AMIDE CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE

Mol%	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	318.15 K
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	9.388	9.665	10.064	10.452	10.759
7.71	8.667	8.994	9.166	9.474	9.852
15.80	7.989	8.234	8.482	8.827	9.182
24.32	7.443	7.668	7.897	8.212	8.561
33.30	6.924	7.176	7.357	7.650	7.850
42.78	6.486	6.694	6.968	7.126	7.357
52.78	6.055	6.265	6.533	6.724	6.923
63.38	5.704	5.906	6.075	6.269	6.445
74.61	5.401	5.550	5.731	5.917	6.084
86.53	5.093	5.239	5.428	5.571	5.762
99.22	4.831	4.997	5.147	5.298	5.512
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	8.196	8.581	8.769	9.074	9.325
7.32	7.582	7.817	8.083	8.340	8.601
14.99	7.027	7.258	7.478	7.169	7.955
23.03	6.564	6.715	6.936	7.733	7.402
31.48	6.130	6.375	6.508	6.331	6.920
40.36	5.787	5.944	6.137	6.892	6.534
49.73	5.405	5.558	5.719	5.405	6.075
59.59	4.961	5.094	5.257	5.156	5.582
70.03	4.717	4.859	5.015	5.923	5.316
81.03	4.512	4.648	4.787	4.627	5.076
92.71	4.249	4.361	4.480	4.470	4.762

It is observed that β and L_f of NaI/LiNO₃ in DMF + ethanol mixtures decrease monotonically with the mol% of DMF in the mixtures at all temperatures studied (Tables 4 and 5) with no maxima or minima. As expected, β and L_f are found to increase with temperature of the systems. Table 6 indicates that with an increase in DMF concentration the value of R_A increases in both the mixtures. The increase in Z with the mol% of DMF is found to be nearly linear, whereas a reverse trend in Z is noticed as the temperature of the system increases (Table 7). It is obvious that the linear increase in Z with mol% of DMF is in agreement with the theoretical requirement (equation 6) because u and ρ both increase with the mol% of DMF in the mixtures investigated. On the other hand, the decrease in Z with the increase in temperature is again attributed to the corresponding decrease in u and ρ with temperature. Table 8 shows that R_m increases linearly with the mol% of DMF in the mixtures. This is expected, since the values of molar volume, V and u both increase with DMF mol% in these systems. This is in accordance with the results obtained by Prakash *et al.*¹⁰ for R_m in alcoholic solutions of Zn(NO₃)₂ and La(NO₃)₃.

TABLE 5—INTERMOLECULAR FREE LENGTH (L_f , 10^{-11} m) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF AMIDE CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE

Mol%	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	318.15 K
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	6.028	6.170	6.350	6.527	6.679
7.71	5.792	5.952	6.061	6.214	6.404
15.80	5.560	5.694	5.830	5.999	6.170
24.32	5.367	5.500	5.625	5.786	5.958
33.30	5.177	5.316	5.430	5.584	5.705
42.78	5.010	5.134	5.282	5.390	5.523
52.78	4.841	4.967	5.117	5.235	5.358
63.38	4.658	4.823	4.934	5.055	5.170
74.61	4.572	4.675	4.792	4.912	5.023
86.53	4.440	4.542	4.664	4.766	4.888
99.22	4.324	4.436	4.541	4.647	4.780
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	5.632	5.788	5.928	6.082	6.218
7.32	5.417	5.548	5.691	5.821	5.972
14.99	5.215	5.346	5.474	5.606	5.743
23.03	5.040	5.143	5.272	5.406	5.540
31.48	4.871	4.984	5.178	5.239	5.357
40.36	4.732	4.838	4.959	5.080	5.254
49.73	4.574	4.679	4.787	4.901	5.019
59.59	4.382	4.479	4.590	4.694	4.811
70.03	4.273	4.374	4.483	4.585	4.695
81.03	4.179	4.278	4.380	4.480	4.588
92.71	4.055	4.141	4.237	4.343	4.444

Since the dielectric constant of DMF is higher than that of ethanol at a given temperature³, the dielectric constant of DMF + ethanol mixture is expected to increase with the increasing amount of DMF in the mixtures. Similar assumption was made by Rohdewald and Moldner¹¹ who calculated the 'approximated dielectric constant' (ADC) of liquid mixtures using the relation,

$$\text{ADC} = [(\% \text{ solvent}_1)(\epsilon_1) + (\% \text{ solvent}_2)(\epsilon_2) + \dots + (\% \text{ solvent}_x)(\epsilon_x)]/100 \quad (8)$$

Thus, the calculated ADCs for 7.71, 52.75 and 99.22 mol% DMF + ethanol mixtures are found to be 25.45, 30.97 and 36.61 at 298.15 K. As a result, the electrostatic effect of the solvent on the dissolved electrolyte is increased. Hence, it may be inferred that electrolyte-solvent interaction increases with the increase in DMF concentration of the mixture. The progressive decrease in β and L_f with increase in DMF mol% for the present systems (Tables 4 and 5) supports the above view.

Furthermore, a qualitative explanation regarding the preferential solvation of cations and anions by the liquid components may be suggested. It has been pointed out^{12,13} on the basis of nmr study of ion-solvent interaction that smaller cations like Li⁺ and Na⁺ are strongly solvated by dipolar aprotic solvents such as DMF, while anions like I⁻ and NO₃⁻ prefer to interact more favourably with protic solvents such as ethanol. In the light of the above fact, a more pronounced decrease in β and L_f (Tables 4 and 5) with in-

TABLE 6—RELATIVE ASSOCIATIONS (R_A) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF AMIDE CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE

Mol% DMF	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	318.15 K
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
7.71	1.030	1.029	1.033	1.033	1.031
15.80	1.063	1.063	1.065	1.065	1.063
24.32	1.094	1.094	1.096	1.096	1.094
33.30	1.123	1.122	1.126	1.126	1.127
42.78	1.152	1.152	1.153	1.156	1.156
52.78	1.184	1.183	1.183	1.185	1.185
63.38	1.213	1.212	1.215	1.217	1.218
74.61	1.240	1.241	1.244	1.245	1.246
86.53	1.273	1.274	1.275	1.278	1.277
99.22	1.297	1.297	1.300	1.303	1.301
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
7.32	1.031	1.033	1.032	1.032	1.032
14.99	1.060	1.062	1.062	1.063	1.062
23.03	1.090	1.093	1.093	1.093	1.093
31.48	1.118	1.119	1.119	1.119	1.119
40.36	1.143	1.145	1.145	1.146	1.145
49.73	1.174	1.176	1.176	1.177	1.177
59.59	1.206	1.208	1.208	1.210	1.209
70.03	1.235	1.237	1.237	1.239	1.239
81.03	1.257	1.259	1.260	1.262	1.261
92.71	1.287	1.290	1.292	1.292	1.292

TABLE 7—SPECIFIC ACOUSTIC IMPEDANCE (Z , $10^6 \text{ kg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF AMIDE CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE

Mol% DMF	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	318.15 K
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	0.923	0.907	0.886	0.867	0.853
7.71	0.970	0.950	0.938	0.920	0.858
15.80	1.022	1.004	0.986	0.964	0.942
24.32	1.069	1.050	1.032	1.009	0.986
33.30	1.118	1.095	1.079	1.056	1.039
42.78	1.165	1.144	1.119	1.103	1.083
52.78	1.217	1.194	1.166	1.146	1.127
63.38	1.265	1.240	1.220	1.198	1.178
74.61	1.310	1.290	1.266	1.243	1.222
86.53	1.263	1.340	1.314	1.293	1.268
99.22	1.408	1.381	1.357	1.334	1.305
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	1.013	1.991	0.974	0.955	0.940
7.32	1.064	1.046	1.026	1.007	0.990
14.99	1.116	1.095	1.077	1.058	1.039
23.03	1.166	1.150	1.129	1.108	1.088
31.48	1.216	1.196	1.175	1.152	1.134
40.36	1.261	1.242	1.219	1.157	1.176
49.73	1.317	1.296	1.274	1.253	1.231
59.59	1.385	1.364	1.340	1.318	1.294
70.03	1.434	1.410	1.385	1.363	1.339
81.03	1.475	1.450	1.426	1.403	1.379
92.71	1.533	1.510	1.487	1.459	1.435

TABLE 8—MOLAR SOUND VELOCITY (R_m , $10^{-4} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} (\text{ms}^{-1})^{1/3}$) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF AMIDE CONCENTRATION AND TEMPERATURE

Mol% DMF	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	318.15 K
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	6.120	6.129	6.128	6.128	6.139
7.71	6.329	6.331	6.351	6.358	6.353
15.80	6.537	6.545	6.554	6.554	6.554
24.32	6.753	6.760	6.774	6.773	6.771
33.30	7.011	7.010	7.022	7.019	7.030
42.78	7.262	7.267	7.262	7.278	7.284
52.78	7.527	7.530	7.524	7.534	7.545
63.38	7.798	7.801	7.811	7.816	7.828
74.61	8.099	8.108	8.112	8.115	8.125
86.53	8.383	8.390	8.390	8.402	8.410
99.22	8.747	8.746	8.753	8.761	8.753
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol					
0.00	5.992	5.987	5.990	5.989	5.986
7.32	6.171	6.173	6.173	6.174	6.177
14.99	6.375	6.375	6.377	6.379	6.380
23.03	6.573	6.583	6.583	6.582	6.583
31.48	6.807	6.811	6.814	6.813	6.819
40.36	7.047	7.053	7.053	7.054	7.056
49.73	7.282	7.287	7.290	7.293	7.294
59.59	7.576	7.582	7.583	7.589	7.588
70.03	7.810	7.812	7.812	7.816	7.816
81.03	8.109	8.110	8.112	8.117	8.117
92.71	8.407	8.413	8.409	8.416	8.419

TABLE 9—ENTHALPY (ΔH° , kJ mol⁻¹), ENTROPY (ΔS° , J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹) AND LINEAR CORRELATION FACTOR (f) OF SODIUM IODIDE AND LITHIUM NITRATE IN DMF + ETHANOL MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF AMIDE CONCENTRATION FROM 298.15 TO 318.15 K

Mol% DMF	ΔH°	ΔS°	f
0.1 M NaI + DMF + Ethanol			
0.00	13.872	3.486	0.999
7.71	12.675	0.081	0.999
15.80	11.927	-1.995	0.999
24.32	11.156	-4.356	0.999
33.30	10.530	-6.295	0.999
42.78	10.347	-6.972	0.999
52.78	9.773	-8.981	0.999
63.38	9.592	-9.831	0.999
74.61	9.172	-11.461	0.999
86.53	9.110	-11.926	0.999
99.22	8.873	-13.078	0.999
1.0 M LiNO ₃ + DMF + Ethanol			
0.00	16.060	5.594	0.999
7.32	15.663	4.479	0.999
14.99	14.736	1.763	0.999
23.03	14.105	-0.196	0.999
31.48	13.429	-2.184	0.999
40.36	13.668	-4.566	0.999
49.73	12.339	-5.520	0.999
59.59	12.150	-6.614	0.999
70.03	12.114	-6.981	0.999
81.03	11.882	-7.857	0.999
92.71	11.832	-8.731	0.996

creasing concentration of DMF in the mixtures may be due to the preferential solvation of Na^+ and Li^+ ions by DMF and those of I^- and NO_3^- ions by ethanol molecules. The increase in the values of β and L_f with increasing temperature may be attributed to the partial dissociation of solvated solvent molecules in the systems.

Finally, the activation parameters like enthalpy (ΔH^*) and entropy (ΔS^*) of activation of viscous flow are found to be quite useful in explaining the mechanism of viscous flow in pure liquids and solutions. Eyring's viscosity equation¹⁴,

$$\eta = (hN/V)\exp(\Delta G^*/RT) \quad (9)$$

when combined with

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^* \quad (10)$$

yields the equation,

$$R \ln (\eta V) = [R \ln (hN) - \Delta S^*] + \Delta H^*/T \quad (11)$$

where, h is the Planck constant, N the Avogadro number, R the gas constant and ΔG^* the free energy of activation of viscous flow. Plots of $R \ln (\eta V)$ against $1/T$ for each mixture and for both the ternary systems were found to be linear, indicating that ΔH^* values are constant in the temperature range 298.15–318.15 K. The values of the slopes, ΔH^* and the intercepts, ΔS^* obtained from these plots, together with the linear correlation factor, f of equation (11) are given in Table 9. The values of ΔH^* are positive for both the ternary systems and decrease with mol% of DMF in the mixture. This suggests that the formation of activated species necessary for viscous flow appears quite easy in the DMF region and becomes difficult as the ethanol mole fraction increases. The values of ΔS^* (Table 9) are found to decrease and become more negative as the mol% of DMF in the mixture increases. This indicates that during viscous flow the liquid is more structured, as a result of the formation of activated species, than it is in the initial state. Similar trends in the variation of ΔH^* and ΔS^* have also been reported for DMF + 1,2-ethanediol⁴ and DMF + ethanol¹ systems.

Experimental

DMF¹⁵ (s.d. fine, A. R. grade) and ethanol¹⁶ (E. Merck) were purified. NaI and LiNO_3 (E. Merck) were used as such, except for drying in vacuum at 343 K. The mixtures were prepared by mass, with a precision of ± 0.05 mg. The probable error in the mole fraction was estimated to be within $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$.

Density was measured with a single stem pycnometer (Pyrex glass) of bulb capacity $8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3$ having a graduated stem with $5.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ dm}^3$ divisions. The marks on the stem were calibrated by using double-distilled water. Viscosity was determined using a Ubbelohde viscometer¹⁷ calibrated with double-distilled water. The overall experimental uncertainty was estimated to be $\pm 1.5 \times$

10^{-3} . The viscometer containing the test liquid was allowed to stand for about 20 min in a thermostatic water-bath to minimize the thermal fluctuation. The ultrasonic velocity was measured using a single-crystal variable-path interferometer at 3 MHz by the reported method¹⁸. The experimental values of density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity of pure DMF [944.6 kg m^{-3} , $0.813 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 1446.5 m s^{-1} (at 303.15 K)] and those of pure ethanol [(785.8 kg m^{-3} , $1.095 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 1152.0 ms^{-1}) at 298.15 K] were found to be in good agreement with the corresponding literature values [(944.5 kg m^{-3} , $0.814 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 1445.0 ms^{-1}) at 303.15 K]^{2,4,19} and [785.2 kg m^{-3} , $1.090 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and 1144.0 ms^{-1}]^{2,20,21}. The temperature of the test liquids and their mixtures was maintained to an accuracy of $\pm 0.05^\circ$ in a thermostatic water-bath.

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